

Simulating the international clade I1b mpox spread patterns in Asia, 2023 and onwards

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Abstract

Objective The global mpox outbreak of clade IIb affected many Asian countries in 2023, following a sustained local transmission in Japan. Given the large population sizes and limited vaccine rollout in Asia, the ongoing transmission of mpox in Asia is of global health concern. We aimed to understand and project the international spread patterns of mpox considering the heterogeneity in sexual activity levels among men who have sex with men (MSM).

Methods We constructed a mathematical model incorporating heterogeneous MSM sexual networks and international travel volume, calibrated to incidence data in Japan. We used this model to simulate the pattern of international spread of mpox across 42 Asian countries and territories, assuming Japan as the origin of the spread.

Findings Our simulations highlighted countries and territories at a high risk of mpox introduction, many of which were low- and middle-income countries (LMICs) in South-eastern Asia. The focus of simulated importation risk showed a gradual shift over time from Eastern Asia to South-eastern Asia, and subsequently to Central, Southern and Western Asia, which roughly coincided with the observed spread patterns in 2023–2024.

Conclusion Our multi-country mpox outbreak model can help project the possible trajectory of international spread in Asia. Global cooperation and support to contain mpox outbreaks of clade IIb are warranted, especially for LMICs with an elevated risk of introduction, to minimise the risk of continued circulation in Asia and beyond.

(231 words)

Keywords: Mpox, men who have sex with men, Asia, international spread, heavy-tailed distribution, sexual contact.

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Introduction

The global mpox outbreak of clade IIb spread among men who have sex with men (MSM) in many countries across Europe and the Americas within several months since its emergence in May 2022.¹ After recording around 40,000 cases worldwide, cases started to decline by the end of 2022.¹ Following this, local transmission generally subsided in those countries, with only some sporadic and limited resurgences occurring from 2023 onwards.² However, as of April 2025, clade IIb continues to drive a prolonged global outbreak predominantly affecting MSM, with cases reported across all world regions.³ While the annual case counts outside Africa—where clade IIb has circulated almost exclusively—have decreased from 2022 (84,017 cases), they remain substantial, with 9,198 cases in 2023 and 10,728 cases in 2024. The pace appears to be comparable in early 2025, with 1,662 cases reported between January and March 2025.⁴

Asia had been the least affected region with only limited numbers of importations and onward transmission reported by the end of 2022. A total of 410 cases were reported in 2022,⁵ mostly from Western Asia, with only Israel experiencing a sustained local transmission, accounting for the majority (262/410) of those cases.^{5,6} However in 2023, following Japan's local outbreak beginning in January (in which only three cases had an

international travel history),⁷ several countries in Eastern and South-eastern Asia experienced sustained transmission of mpox. Notably, China reported the largest epidemic in the region with 2,806 cases by the end of 2024,^{5,8} followed by Thailand with 853 cases. Phylogenetic analysis⁹ showed that most viral samples from those Asian countries were distinct from the lineages that circulated in other regions in 2022 and were linked to samples from Japan, suggesting that the mpox epidemics in Asian countries since 2023 could be characterised as a divergent regional outbreak. Despite the World Health Organization (WHO)'s lifting of the first public health emergency of international concern (PHEIC) against mpox on 11 May 2023,¹⁰ reflecting the declining trend in previously-affected countries in the rest of the regions, the international spread remained a growing threat to Asia in 2023. Many Asian countries had large susceptible populations at risk, most of which are low- and middle-income countries with limited access to vaccines.⁷ These unique conditions warranted quantitative risk assessments for the regional outbreak of mpox.

Mathematical models of the international spread of emerging infectious diseases have conventionally combined local transmission dynamics and global importations characterised by international travel volume data.^{11,12} These models have been successful in understanding and predicting the temporospatial patterns of the global spread of respiratory pathogens like SARS-CoV-2¹³⁻¹⁵ and influenza.^{11,16} However, they often assume homogenous mixing explicitly or implicitly, limiting their applicability to the global mpox outbreak of clade I1b, where highly heterogeneous sexual networks among MSM play a substantial role in shaping the transmission dynamics.¹⁷⁻²¹ In such sexual networks, individuals with higher numbers of sexual partners are more likely to be infected and to acquire immunity in the early phase of an outbreak,^{22,23} leaving those with fewer partners in the susceptible pool; the risk of onward transmission per infector thus declines as the outbreak progresses. A previous modelling study showed that this selective transmission process needs to be considered to explain the international spread of clade I1b mpox in 2022.²⁴ As the mpox outbreak in Asia from 2023 continued to predominantly affect the MSM community, this depletion-of-susceptible due to heterogeneous sexual networks should also be accounted for in analysing its international spread patterns.

In this study, we developed a stochastic model of mpox transmission over sexual contact networks among MSM accounting for travel volume to simulate its international spread patterns across Asia. This study was originally initiated to prospectively assess the future importation risks across Asian countries from July 2023 onward using data available by the time of the analysis.²⁵ Specifically, we fitted the developed model to the mpox incidence data in Japan and confirmed that the simulated international spread generally aligned with countries reporting importations as of July 2023. We then ran our simulation forward to project future mpox international spread patterns in Asia. In this manuscript, we retain this context of our simulation by preserving the original data period and discuss our results retrospectively by comparing them to the observed progression of the outbreak since the time of the initial analysis.

Methods

Data source

Mpox incidence data were collected by date of medical attendance in Japan from the Ministry of Health, Labour and Welfare (MHLW) website from 25th July 2022 to 7th July 2023 (https://github.com/akira-endo/mpoxlinelist_JPN). We used the sexual partnership distribution estimated from the self-reported number of sexual partners over 4 weeks of the

UK National Survey of Sexual Attitudes and Lifestyles (Natsal) datasets to model the mixing among the MSM population.²⁶ We also used the sexual partnership distribution over 1 year estimated from Natsal as part of our sensitivity analysis.¹⁷ The international travel volume in 2019 was obtained from the World Tourism Organization (UNWTO).²⁷ Asian countries and territories included in the present study were based on the United Nations' definition²⁸ but excluding North Korea, Afghanistan, Pakistan, Iraq, Israel, Turkmenistan and Yemen due to the missing international travel volume data.

To qualitatively validate our international projections of mpox, we collected the dates of the first mpox report since 2023 in Asian countries and territories from various sources. We also collected the cumulative number of mpox infections from the Our World in Data website.⁵

In addition, we used the National Inventory of Japanese Sexual Behavior (NInJaS) data²⁹ to assess the plausibility of our assumption that the sexual partnership distribution in Asia follows the UK Natsal dataset (see Figure S17). The Regional Ethics Committee at the University of Tokyo, Japan approved the study (ref: 2019305NI-(2)). All the data used in this study is publicly available, except for the NInJaS study under an ethics-associated restriction on data sharing (see the original study²⁹ for details).

Model of international spread of clade IIb mpox

We constructed a stochastic meta-population SEIR model representing MSM populations in 42 Asian countries/territories. As the availability of MSM population size estimates substantially varies among these countries and territories, we assumed that MSM account for one percent of the total population (i.e. two percent of the male population) in every country/territory considered.³⁰ To account for the heterogeneity in sexual behaviours driving mpox transmission dynamics,¹⁸ the population in each country/territory was stratified into 50 compartments of different sexual activity levels. These levels, reflecting the number of sexual partners over the assumed infectious period of mpox of 10 days,³¹ were assumed to linearly correlate with both the hazard of infection and onward transmission. We used the reported 4-week partner numbers from the UK Natsal data to parameterise the distribution of sexual activity levels among MSM populations in Asia, given the scarcity of similar datasets in this region. We did not consider the effect of vaccination in our analysis because the only approved mpox vaccine (LC16) in Japan as of 2023³² was administered in trial settings and not widely accessible as a preventive measure. Mpox importations between countries and territories were modelled based on the 2019 travel volume data from the UNWTO.²⁷ We assumed that the importation of mpox from one country/territory to another could be contributed to by either inbound or outbound travellers, and that its risk was proportional to the number of travellers between the countries and territories.

We simulated the international spread of mpox in Asia using a Bayesian data assimilation approach.^{33,34} We first fitted our model to the reported mpox incidence in Japan from 16 January (date of medical attendance for the first case in 2023) to 26 June 2023 using the approximated Bayesian computation³⁴ to obtain posterior samples of the sexually-associated secondary attack risk (SAR; transmission risk per sexual partnership) for mpox. For consistency with the observed local transmission in the Republic of Korea (South Korea) as of the end of the fitting period (26 June 2023), we also conditioned the posterior samples on the early introduction to South Korea; i.e. the model was required to have 10 or more cases in South Korea by 26 June 2023. We then simulated mpox transmission from 16 January onwards in Japan and other Asian countries and territories with these posterior samples and the international travel volume data,²⁷ assuming for simplicity that cases in Japan initiated the

international mpox spread in Asia in 2023 and that importations from outside Asia were negligible. Further methodological details can be found in *Supplementary materials*.

Results

Simulated importation probabilities in Asian countries and territories

Our model calibration using mpox incidence data in Japan from 16th January to 26th June 2023 yielded a posterior median estimate for sexually-associated SAR of 72% (95% credible interval: 47–93%), which was comparable to the observation from a contact tracing study in Belgium during the 2022 outbreak (66%; 12 positives among 18 contacts).³⁵

Using these posterior samples, we computed the simulated importation probabilities for each country/territory, which we defined as the proportion of simulations where the country/territory experienced at least one importation of a case (Figure 1). Countries and territories with the highest simulated importation probabilities were mostly concentrated in Eastern and South-eastern Asia. Of note, 6 countries (mainland China, Thailand, Vietnam, Philippines, Malaysia, and Indonesia) among the top 10 were low- and middle-income countries and territories (LMICs); likewise, 13 among the top 20 were LMICs. We also found that many of these countries and territories indeed observed mpox introductions in 2023 (Figure S9).

Figure 1. Simulated mpox importation probabilities in Asia. The node size represents the simulated importation probability for each country/territory under the condition of having ≥ 10 mpox cases in South Korea (hatched node). The widths of links between nodes indicate the average yearly travel volume between countries and territories. The countries and territories with ≥ 1 known importation from any Asian countries or territories and with ≥ 1 known importation (either unknown to be from Asia or known to be from outside Asia) are shown in red and yellow, respectively. A red star represents the assumed initial source of spread from Japan. Links for travel volume of less than 10,000 persons per year were omitted from the figure. Grey square points represent Asian countries not included in our simulations.

Projected patterns of international spread within Asia

We visualised the international spread patterns of mpox in Asia using an Alluvial diagram (Figure 2). We defined an international spread event as the first occurrence of importation of an mpox case since 2023 between a specific importation-exportation country/territory pair. The boxes and paths in the Alluvial diagram represent the simulated probability of the international spread events and their generational orders (assuming Japan as the initial source of spread, i.e. “Generation 0” in Figure 2) among the simulations. The majority of the 1st-generation importations (i.e. direct importations from Japan) were to Eastern Asian countries and territories, whereas South-eastern Asian countries were predominant in the 2nd generation. The share of Central, Southern and Western Asian countries increased in the 3rd generation onwards, although with relatively small simulated importation probabilities. These simulated patterns generally aligned with reported dates of new mpox introductions in 2023 in Asia (Table S2).

Figure 2. International spread patterns of mpox in Asia. Each column represents the generation of international spread. The height of each box denotes the simulated probability of international spread events for each generation conditional to ≥ 10 mpox cases in South Korea (hatched boxes). The width of the outflow from the right-hand side of each box (country/territory) denotes the relative frequency of exportation. Green boxes correspond to Eastern Asia, blue boxes to South-eastern Asia and red boxes to Central, Southern and Western Asia.

Discussion and conclusion

Our multi-country mpox transmission model accounting for heterogeneous sexual contact networks suggested the possible patterns of international spread in Asia. A simulated outbreak was assumed to have originated in Japan, which showed the earliest sustained local

outbreak among Asian countries and territories in 2023. Our results highlighted that countries and territories at high risk of importation, some of which coincided with the observed importations since 2023, include LMICs mostly located in South-eastern Asia. This is particularly concerning given the large population sizes and limited access to mpox vaccines in these countries and territories. A large outbreak in China in the summer of 2023,⁵ followed by reports of cases in a few neighbouring countries,³⁶ was an example of such regional concern. While the absolute magnitude of simulated importations should be interpreted with caution as we observed substantial variation in outbreak sizes between simulation runs due to stochastic fluctuation associated with importation events (Figure S14), the relative patterns of importations were overall suggested to be robust, including in our sensitivity analysis (see *Supplementary materials*). We therefore believe that, despite caveats, our simulation would help anticipate the possible future trajectory of mpox international spread in Asia. Indeed, new introductions of mpox cases in 2023 through 2024 have been reported initially from Eastern Asian countries and territories followed by South-eastern Asian countries, consistent with our simulation results thus far. Whether this further develops into established transmission in South-eastern Asia and then in Central, Southern and Western Asia warrants close attention from the global health community to monitor the risk of global resurgence of clade IIb mpox.

The 2022 global mpox outbreak of clade IIb has affected many countries, mostly in Europe and the Americas, where it is no longer considered an imminent public health threat¹⁰ due to likely established immunity through either natural infection or vaccination.¹⁸ However, there have been multiple events that suggest a potential risk of reemergence, e.g. new cases in areas where the epidemic appeared to have ceased (e.g. European and U.S. regions^{37,38}) and reports of breakthrough infections and reinfections.³⁹ Even if the transmission potential of mpox has been once depleted due to accumulated immunity in a population, multiple factors including waning immunity, turnover of sexually active individuals or the emergence of immune escaping variants could still drive the reemergence in the long term. Indeed, possibly because of these factors, several countries including Canada, Brazil and Australia experienced a major resurgence in 2024, with Australia reporting its highest-ever monthly case count of 302, five times the peak monthly count recorded during the first wave in 2022.⁴ Continued circulation of mpox in Asian countries (e.g. China) is therefore of concern not only for this region but also for other regions including those that have already been affected in 2022. Global support for control effort in LMICs in Asia, as well as other regions at increased risk, remains essential.

This study holds several limitations. First, assuming the same sexual partner distribution and per-capita MSM population size across Asia may not fully reflect the potential heterogeneity across diverse socio-cultural backgrounds in Asian countries and territories. Existing datasets on MSM partnerships in Asia did not contain the full distribution to inform our model, requiring us to use the UK Natsal dataset as a proxy. However, we found that those existing datasets from Japan,²⁹ China, Singapore, Malaysia, Taiwan and other Asian countries and territories^{40,41} generally suggested similarity in partner distributions after the reporting time window for partners was adjusted for, including settings where homosexuality is criminalised⁴² (Figure S17-18). Furthermore, we opted to use 1% of the total population as the MSM population size for all countries and territories, due to uncertainty and biases in country-specific estimates even if available,³⁰ especially from countries and territories where MSM are heavily stigmatised.⁴³ Second, we did not consider the effect of preexisting infection- or vaccine-derived immunity or behavioural changes, which have been discussed in previous mpox modelling studies in Western settings.^{19-21,44,45} In Asia, prior immunity was

likely negligible in most of the included countries and territories because of the limited case counts (Table S2) and vaccine rollout by 2023. It remains unclear whether there were measurable behavioural changes in response to the mpox outbreak in Asia in 2023, particularly after the first WHO PHEIC was lifted.¹⁰ Moreover, as our simulation was originally designed as prospective projections as of July 2023,²⁵ predicting future behavioural responses was out of scope. However, we partially accounted for possible behavioural changes in our sensitivity analysis where we assumed that they may have influenced the later phase of the mpox incidence data in Japan (Figure S13). Third, as the 2023 UNWTO travel volume data was not available at the time of analysis, we used the 2019 data as an alternative. While the travel volume in 2023 may differ from that of 2019 due to the remaining impact of the COVID-19 pandemic (Figure S15), our sensitivity analysis with additional flight passenger data⁴⁶ suggested the use of 2019 travel volume data instead of 2023 might have a minor influence on the results (Figure S16). Finally, while our simulation restricted mpox spread to within Asia, importations from outside the region may not have been negligible. Particularly, observed importations in Western Asian countries should be interpreted with caution, given their geographical proximity to Europe and prior documented importations of European origin.⁶ Some of the earliest importations observed in Western Asia that significantly preceded our simulation range (Figure S9) might be attributable to introductions from Europe.

Our simulation highlighted recent and ongoing risks of mpox importation in Asia, including LMICs with large population sizes and limited access to vaccines. Although the overall case trend in Asia has shown a gradual decline since late 2023, the most recent data suggests persisting transmission in the region,³ leaving remaining susceptible populations at continued risk of importation and local spread. The projected risks and potential importation pathways identified in this study would help assess the risk phase of mpox spread in Asia in response to future outbreak developments. Despite the intensifying global concern on the more recent emergence of mpox clade Ib, the clade currently posing a greater public health threat in Asia remains to be clade IIb as of April 2025. Enhanced surveillance, concerted global efforts, and vaccine equity are crucial to contain future mpox outbreaks.

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Conflict of interest

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Author contributions

Conceptualisation: A.E.; Data curation: T.R.A., S-m.J., C.G., H.S., A.T., F.M., A.E.; Formal analysis: T.R.A., S-m.J.; Funding acquisition: A.E.; Methodology: T.R.A., S-m.J., H.M., F.M., A.E.; Project administration: A.E.; Software: T.R.A., S-m.J.; Supervision: A.E.; Validation: T.R.A.; Visualisation: T.R.A., S-m.J.; Writing - Original Draft Preparation: T.R.A., S-m.J., A.E.; Writing - Review & Editing: S-m.J., H.M., C.G., H.S., A.T., F.M., A.E.

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